

Environmentally sustainable electroplating of selective cobalt-chromium coating on stainless steel for efficient solar collectors

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ABSTRACT

Half of today's global energy consumption is in the form of heating and cooling. Solar collectors are the most promising sustainable alternative to fossil fuels in this sector. The most important component in a solar collector is the receiver, which by use of a selective surface absorbs and converts solar irradiance to thermal energy. Herein, a novel selective surface for low-to mid-temperature solar collectors is developed, studied and presented. The surface is produced by electroplating a cobalt-chromium coating on a stainless steel substrate using an electrolyte based on a deep eutectic solvent. Our method makes use of trivalent instead of traditionally used hexavalent chromium, which significantly reduces health-related issues and makes it more environmentally benign. We obtain a coating of chromium doped cobalt where the surface exhibits an absorptance and emittance of 0.96 and 0.14, respectively, giving it a solar-to-thermal efficiency of 0.95. An observed loss in optical efficiency, is shown to correlate to an oxidation of the metallic cobalt to Co_3O_4 at elevated temperatures. We further show that this oxidation can be mitigated by dip-coating a protective silica top coating, which concurrently improves the optical selectivity of the surface. The present selective surface is efficient, cheap, scalable, and easy to produce sustainably, making it competitive to industry standards. We foresee that our method will have impact on the advancement of improved low-to mid-temperature solar collectors, assisting a faster transition towards a sustainable society.

1. Introduction

A common misconception is that new revolutionizing technologies such as fusion and carbon capture, must emerge to save us from the imminent climate catastrophe caused by our overconsumption of fossil fuels. Albeit such game-changing techniques are important for the transition into a sustainable energy production in a longer perspective, a fast transition is already within reach by implementing gradual improvements of current renewable technologies so that they become more commercially competitive over non-sustainable fossil alternatives. Typical examples are the production of electricity from renewable sources such as wind and solar cells, which nowadays frequently outcompete electricity production from fossil sources, due to a continuous increase in efficiency and lowering of production costs [1].

Despite progress in electricity production, it is noteworthy that today, 50% of the consumed energy is in the form of thermal energy [2]. Energy which, except for the most extreme temperatures used in

industry, could be produced with concentrating solar thermal (CST) systems. However, even the most mature of the CST technologies, the parabolic trough collectors (PTCs) [3], need improvements in regard to system configuration, integration and component efficiency. The most essential component in solar collectors are the receivers, which absorb solar irradiation and transform it into heat. This process can be made more efficient by implementing a solar selective surface which increases the solar absorptance (wavelengths <2500 nm) and decreases the thermal emittance (wavelengths >2500 nm).

The solar selective absorber was introduced by Tabor [4] and Shaffer [5] in the 1950s. Tabor suggested a low emittance metal substrate with a thin coating, absorbing short wavelengths while being largely transparent in IR, such as black chrome, black nickel, or copper oxide [6]. A high durability, low cost, high solar weighted absorptance (α_S) and low total emittance at 100 °C (ϵ_{100}) of 0.96–0.97 and 0.10 [7,8], respectively, made black chrome the choice for commercialization [6]. However, issues with hexavalent chromium being carcinogenic and toxic

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have resulted in legal restrictions [9]. Instead, coatings deposited by physical vapor deposition (PVD) techniques are primarily used today [6, 10], as they are advantageous with regards to durability [11–13] and sustainability. They suffer, however, from large capital cost [14].

Electroplated alternatives to the hexavalent black chrome, without the health-related issues, such as cobalt (Co), Nickel (Ni) and trivalent chromium (Cr(III)) have been investigated. Black Co have been closest in terms of optical properties with reports of $\alpha_S = 0.95 - 0.96$ and $\epsilon_{100} = 0.1 - 0.18$ [15–17]. Recently however, Cr(III) absorbers from aqueous solutions have been in focus and co-depositions with Co [18–20] or ZnO [21] have been reported. While high absorptance is reported, the emittance data is not, making both the selectivity and suitability in CST unclear. The limited stable electrochemical potential window of water also makes the Cr(III) deposition inefficient and associated with high hydrogen evolution.

An alternate route to electroplated Cr(III) is to use ionic liquids, which have considerably higher potential windows. Deposition of black chromium with this approach was demonstrated by Surviliene et al. [22] without reporting optical properties and Eugénio et al. who achieved $\alpha = 0.97$ and $\epsilon = 0.19$ at $0.8-4 \mu\text{m}$ and $>10 \mu\text{m}$, respectively [23].

Here we demonstrate an electroplating method based on a subgroup within the ionic liquids known as deep eutectic solvent (DES), introduced by Abbott et al., in 2003 [24]. The DESs comprises a mixture of a halide salt and a hydrogen bond donor [25] and exhibit appealing characteristics such as being cheap, sustainable, nontoxic, high metal solubility and a large potential window [26]. DESs have been used to electroplate various metals [9,26–34], but to our knowledge not for the purpose of producing solar selective surfaces for solar thermal applications.

Our deposition method comprises a selective Co–Cr coating deposited on stainless steel using a simple and sustainable electrolyte, complemented with a dip-coated silica top coating to increase the thermal stability of the absorbers. We show that the engineered receiver surface exhibits excellent optical properties well-adapted for low-to mid-temperature PTCs, with a concurrent good stability.

2. Experimental

2.1. Deposition of Co–Cr coating

A 0.1 mm thick AISI 304 stainless steel (SS) was used as substrate, and a titanium mesh coated with platinum (Umicore Platinode® N-type mesh) as a counter electrode. Prior to deposition the substrate was

sonicated in acetone for 15 min, electropolished, rinsed in deionized water, passivated in 13 wt% hydrochloric acid (HCl) for 1 min, rinsed in deionized water and dried with nitrogen. The electropolishing was performed in accordance with Lin et al. in a bath comprising H_3PO_4 : H_2SO_4 :glycerol at a molar ratio of 2:1:1 kept at 30°C during a 5 min polish at 0.5 A/cm^2 anodic current density [35]. The deposition of the Co–Cr coating was performed with chronopotentiometry in a two-electrode electrochemical cell using a potentiostat (Autolab Metrohm POSTAT302 N). A design of experiment approach was used to optimize the deposition parameters, see Table S2. The coating was deposited for 10 min with a cathodic current density of 4.6 mA/cm^2 in an electrolyte kept at 44°C . The electrolyte comprised choline chloride (ChCl), ethylene glycol (EG), cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate ($\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and chromium(III) chloride hexahydrate ($\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) at a molar ratio of 10:160:6:3 which was stirred prior to, but not during, deposition. After the deposition, the samples were rinsed in deionized water and dried with nitrogen. For a schematic of the synthesis see Fig. 1a.

2.2. Silica top coating

The silica (SiO_2) top coating was deposited by dip-coating from a sol containing 0.01 M hydrochloric acid (HCl), ethanol and tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) at a mass ratio of 268:222:510. The sol was prepared by adding the HCl to the ethanol and stirring until thoroughly mixed, before adding the TEOS and stirring for at least 1 h, or until transparent and homogenous. Prior to deposition, the samples were rinsed in ethanol and plasma cleaned for 2 min using a tabletop plasma cleaner (PDC-32G, Harrick Plasma). The samples were dipped at a speed of 45 mm/min with a KSV NIMA dip coater and then calcinated for 1 h at 120°C .

2.3. Thermal stability testing

The thermal stability of the coating was evaluated by exposing the samples to 400°C in air for 24 h in a muffle furnace (Nabertherm P330). To quantify the optical degradation of an aging test, a performance criterion (PC) function is used [36]

$$PC = -\Delta\alpha_S + x\Delta\epsilon_{100}, \quad (1)$$

where x is a weighting factor. Commonly, x is taken to be 0.5 [36], but it can be calculated for a specific case, in particular for CST where it

Fig. 1. Cobalt-chromium coating structure. Schematic of the key steps in the synthesis process and the effect on the sample (a). The surface morphology of the texture based selective Co–Cr coating consists of elongated sharp growth regions up to approximately $1 \mu\text{m}$ in length with cavities between (b). The cross section of the $1.8 \mu\text{m}$ thick Co–Cr coating reveals a porosity decreasing with depth (c, d). Note, the scale bar in d is valid for vertical distances due to sample tilt.

deviates from this value. Here, x was calculated to 0.07 based on the intended application in a small parabolic trough with a working temperature of 100 °C, see supporting information for further details.

The thermal degradation of the coating was also evaluated using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). The coating was scraped off from the substrate and grinded in a mortar before performing the TGA at a rate of 10 °C/min up to 900 °C in air provided at a rate of 40 cm³/min.

2.4. Adhesion of the coating

A cross hatch test was used to evaluate the adhesion of the coating both with and without silica top coating. The test was performed in accordance with the ASTM D3359 standard [37]. In short, a crisscross pattern with 1 mm between the lines was cut down to the substrate, after which a tape is applied in the center of the pattern for 60 s and then removed in a rapid fashion. The adhesion of the coating is graded based on how much of the patterned surface is peeled.

2.5. Evaluation of optical properties

The hemispherical reflectance was measured at near normal incidence angle (8°) with a PerkinElmer Lambda 900 spectrophotometer equipped with a 150 mm integrating sphere over 0.3–2.5 μm and a Bruker Fourier-transform infrared spectroscope (FTIR) with a gold coated integrating sphere over 2.5–23 μm. The total emittance was calculated at 100 °C and the AM1.5 direct solar spectrum was used to calculate the solar weighted absorptance [38].

The performance of a selective surface is traditionally evaluated with the selectivity (α_S/ϵ_{100}). However, the selectivity disregards the fact that α_S and ϵ_{100} vary in importance depending on application. A more nuanced evaluation quantity is the solar-to-thermal conversion efficiency (η_{s-t}) given by [39]

$$\eta_{s-t} = \frac{C \sum_s \alpha(\lambda) I_s(\lambda) - \sum_s \epsilon(\lambda) I_B(\lambda, T_A)}{C \sum_s I_s(\lambda)}, \quad (2)$$

where C is the concentrating factor, λ is the wavelength, I_s is the spectral solar irradiance, I_B is the spectral black-body spectrum and T_A is the absorber working temperature. Equation (2) shows that by increasing C or by decreasing T_A , the importance of α increases relative to ϵ .

The optical properties of the samples used to evaluate the thermal stability with the silica top coating was measured using an Optosol Absorber Control K1. To enable distinction, the absorptance and emittance measured with this system are denoted α_{S7} and ϵ_{avg} , respectively.

2.6. Material characterization

The morphology and crystalline structure were investigated using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmittance electron microscopy (TEM), respectively. The SEM imaging of the surface and cross section was done with an acceleration voltage of 5 kV and performed in a Carl Zeiss Merlin FESEM (field emission SEM) using the in-lens secondary electron detector. A Titan Krios 300 kV TEM with a Ceta detector was used on an 80 nm thick lamella of the coating to see the crystalline structure. A Thermo Fisher FEI Scios FIB-SEM (focus ion beam) was used to expose the cross section and to cut out the lamella. To avoid deformation and degradation of the sample during the milling process, a protective Pt layer was deposited over the region, using the same FIB.

Further analysis was done with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Raman spectroscopy. An Oxford Instruments X-Max equipment in the Merlin FESEM using an acceleration voltage and current of 15 kV and 300 pA, respectively was used for the EDX measurements. The XPS analysis was performed with a Kratos Axis Ultra DLD electron spectrometer using monochromated Al K α source at 150 W. The binding energy scale calibration was performed in accordance with ISO Standard

15,472:2010 [40]. The Raman spectra were measured in a Renishaw InVia Raman Spectrometer with a charge-couple device detector a 514 nm laser as an excitation source. The XRD was performed in a PANalytical X'pert3 powder X-ray diffractometer with a PIXcel1D detector.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Coating morphology

Solar absorber coatings are categorized based on the structural design, which is related to how the optical selectivity is achieved. The different designs include intrinsic, semiconductor, multilayer, cermet, dielectric-metal-dielectric and textured absorbers [41]. Based on the surface morphology, visible in the SEM image in Fig. 1b, the SS/Co–Cr coating is texture-based. This is manifested by elongated, sharp growth regions forming protruding ridges up to approximately 1 × 0.1 μm in size with cavities in between. This morphology is well suited to trap wavelengths smaller than the surface structures in multiple reflections resulting in high absorptance, while longer wavelengths perceive the surface as smooth and is therefore reflected [41]. With surface structures up to 1–2 μm, the high absorptance region should capture most of the solar spectrum before shifting to highly reflecting >2 μm, making the size of the structures suitable for a solar selective surface. We also note that irregular structures, in terms of shape and orientation, have been shown to give a broad absorption peak [42].

We note further that the coating is homogeneous and crack free, which is achieved by deposition without stirring. With stirring, the coverage of the coating becomes poor, especially at the edge of the working electrode facing the “stream”. This is believed to be caused by the poor throwing power associated with electrodeposition from DESs in general [26], which originates from the high dynamic viscosity of ethaline (EG mixed with ChCl) compared to water, 0.72 mPas and 30.9 mPas respectively at 35 °C, resulting in lower conductivity and consequently low throwing power [43]. However, the large potential window of the DES still enables a deposition with low hydrogen evolution and consequently high current efficiency, typically >90% for Cr(III) in DES [26].

The high current efficiency is advantageous as it enables close control of the deposition, which is sensitive to changes in current density. Increasing the current density, while staying within the potential window, results in larger surface structures, as the ions have less time to evenly distribute over the electrode and are reduced at protrusions to a larger extent, as manifested in Fig. S1. Consequently, the transition from absorbing to reflecting can be shifted towards longer wavelengths by increasing the current density, which corresponds to an increase in solar absorptance at the expense of a higher emittance. The same trend is evident for a Co absorber with a similar surface morphology, but deposited from an aqueous solution [44].

The selectivity is also affected by the coating thickness. A thin coating interacts less with the radiation, making the reflectance of the surface shift faster towards that of the substrate with increasing wavelength. Consequently, a thin coating is desirable as long as the solar absorptance is maintained, commonly resulting in an ideal thickness of 0.5–2 μm [23].

Fig. 1c and d depicts the cross section of a SS/Co–Cr sample. It reveals that the absorbing Co–Cr coating is 1.8 μm thick, porous and that the porosity decreases with depth into the coating. Such a porosity gradient is expected for a texture-based absorber, as the morphology promotes a first reflection deep in the structure, giving a higher probability of multiple interactions and consequently a high absorptance. Alternatively, the high absorptance can be explained with Fresnel's reflectance equation for normal incidence [45], where continuously increasing effective refractive index with depth, caused in this case by the porosity gradient, gives a lower total reflectance than an abrupt shift would.

3.2. Chemical composition

The elemental composition of the surface and cross section of the coating was analyzed by EDX, as presented in Table 1. The spectra and corresponding mapping regions can be seen in Figs. S2 and S3. The most abundant element is Co, corresponding to 62.3 and 63.1% signals for the surface and cross section, respectively. The same signals for Cr are significantly lower at 2.3 and 6.7%, respectively. Here we note that the cross section Cr signal is partially including the presence of Cr in the substrate. This conclusion is supported by the 1.3 and 16.5% iron signals from the surface and cross section measurements showing a penetration depth larger than the coating thickness in both cases. Still, the decreasing Cr/Fe ratio for the surface, cross section, and substrate signals of 1.77, 0.41 and 0.29, respectively, clearly supports the presence of Cr in the coating. The fact that the ratio of Co/Cr does not match the salt concentration in the electrolyte is explained by earlier observations showing that Co is favored over Cr in co-depositions at low current densities [20]. This is attributed to a lower ion mobility for Cr and a higher reduction potential for the two step Cr(III) reduction reaction compared to the one-step Co reduction reaction [30]. Additionally, since Cr(III) reduces in a two-step process the deposition in ethaline have been observed to be a slow process [46].

Further support for the presence and role of Cr in the coating is manifested by the observation that when Cr is removed from the electrolyte the resulting Co-coating do not adhere at all to the substrate and simply slides off when rinsing the sample. This clearly indicates that Cr is important in the formation of nucleation sites. This is in line with previous reports demonstrating that Cr is an effective adhesion layer for oxide surfaces [47–49].

The carbon signal on the surface is primarily attributed to hydrocarbon contamination after the preparation, which is supported by XPS. The oxygen is related to oxidation in the top surface layer formed when the film is exposed to ambient atmosphere, likely in the form of $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$ [50]. This is supported by a significant darkening of the coating after exposure to the atmosphere, from dull grey (metallic Co) to dark brownish black.

A more detailed understanding of the chemical composition of the surface of the coating is obtained by XPS, see Fig. S6a for the entire spectrum. In Fig. 2a, b and 2c the XPS signals of Co 2p, Cr 2p and O 1s, respectively, are presented. The low Cr signal is in line with the EDX data. The large main Co peak at 779.5 eV and its four satellite peaks indicates Co_3O_4 [51]. However, the intensity, width and position of the peak at 780.9 eV, which lies in the middle of 781.2 and 780.7 eV reported for the first satellite and main peaks of Co_3O_4 and $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$ respectively, suggests a mixture of the two [51,52]. The O 1s peaks at 529.7 and 531.1 eV also agrees well with the main O 1s peaks of Co_3O_4 and $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$ [52].

The XRD spectra in Fig. 2d clearly show that the peaks at 43.55° , 50.65° and 74.55° originates from the stainless steel substrate and are superimposed on the SS/Co–Cr signal. The peaks at 41.65° , 44.21° and 47.28° are from the Co–Cr coating, and originates from the (100), (002) and (101) planes of the hexagonal close packed (hcp) crystal structure expected for metallic Co at ambient temperature [53,54]. Hcp Co have three additional peaks; the two at 51.26° (200) and 62.52° (102) are

indistinguishable here due to the thin, granular coating, while the peak at 75.87° (110) is largely hidden within the peak envelope from the substrate [53]. The large full width half maximum (FWHM) of the peaks assigned to the coating manifests a small grain size for the crystalline Co. We note also that Co_3O_4 and $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$, indicated by the XPS, are not visible in the XRD spectrum showing that these compounds are spatially limited to the surface [52].

The crystallinity in the bulk is further supported by the TEM images of the lamella presented in Fig. 2e and f. Fig. 2e also shows relatively small crystalline domains, in line with the high porosity and XRD spectra of the coating. The distance between lattice planes measured in Fig. 2f reveals a lattice distance of 2.05 Å which is in line with literature for hcp Co(α) phase [55], the expected form of metallic Co at ambient temperatures [56]. However, the small crystalline domains and the thickness of the lamella (approximately 80 nm) makes identification of individual lattice planes impossible.

3.3. Optical properties

The reflectance spectra used for the spectral analysis of the SS/Co–Cr absorber before and after a thermal stability (TS) test is presented in Fig. 3. To better understand its suitability as an absorber, it is presented with normalized spectra of a black body at 100°C and the AM1.5 direct solar irradiance [38]. The surface exhibits a high absorptance over the solar spectrum with a reflectance of approximately 0.02 over 0.3–1 μm . The transition towards high reflectance which occurs over the interval 1–10 μm is gradual rather than sharp. Both the broad absorptance region without interference pattern and the shift towards higher reflectance starting shortly after 1 μm are in line with our predictions based on the textured surface morphology. At wavelengths $>10 \mu\text{m}$ the reflectance has reached its asymptotic value of approximately 0.9, resulting in a highly selective surface. The reflectance is exclusively diffuse up to approximately 0.8 μm before shifting to primarily specular as the wavelengths become longer than the size regime of the surface structures, see Fig. S7a.

In terms of optical properties, the surface exhibits $\alpha_S = 0.963$ (2) and $\epsilon_{100} = 0.144$ (12), a noteworthy high solar absorptance, characteristic for texture-based absorbers [41,57]. Considering an intrinsic emittance of $\epsilon_{100} = 0.12 - 0.13$ for stainless steel [58], a coating thickness of 1.8 μm and lack of additional layers, the emittance is low. A thinner coating would lower it further, close to the limit of the substrate itself, however at the expense of a lower absorptance.

The intended application for the absorber is a small parabolic trough with a working temperature of 100°C and a concentrating factor of 12.5. The suitability of the absorber for this case was evaluated with the solar-to-thermal conversion efficiency, equation (2), which is $\eta_{s-t} = \alpha_S - 0.1\epsilon_{100} = 0.949$ (1) (see derivation in supporting information). The importance of the absorptance is evident from the weighting factor of 0.1, which means that a 1% reduction in α_S to 0.953 would require a $\epsilon_{100} = 0.040$ to maintain the efficiency, which is not feasible with the current absorber design.

This highlights the importance of using a more nuanced evaluation metric than the traditional selectivity (α_S/ϵ_{100}). The selectivity of the SS/Co–Cr absorber is 6.5, compared to 11.8 for the PVD absorber used

Table 1

EDX analysis of the elemental composition, in at%, on the surface and the different regions of the cross section.

Scan location	Composition [at%]									
	C	O	Cl	Cr	Fe	Co	Mn	Ni	Ga	Pt
Co–Cr Surface	15.4	17.7	0.6	2.3	1.3	62.7				
Cross section Pt layer ^a	78.8	0.4		0.5	1.4	1.5			5.0	12.1
Cross section Co–Cr	8.8	0.8	0.2	6.7	16.5	63.1		1.2	1.8	0.9
Cross section substrate	3.2	0.2		19.1	66.9	2.3	1.3	5.9	0.9	0.3

^a The protective Pt layer necessary for the FIB milling comprises gallium, platinum and carbon, and the presence of these elements in the cross section of the Co–Cr coating and the substrate are attributed to curtaining.

Fig. 2. Chemical composition of cobalt-chromium coating. The XPS spectra of Co 2p (a), Cr 2p (b) and O 1s (c) suggests that the majority of the surface is a mixture of Co_3O_4 and $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$. The XRD peaks at 41.65° , 44.21° and 47.28° originating from the Co–Cr coating agrees well with hcp Co and the large FWHM indicates a small grain size (d). The TEM imaging shows a crystalline structure with lattice distance of 2.05 \AA , in line with hcp Co, however the lamella thickness and small crystalline domains makes identification of individual lattice planes impossible (e, f).

Fig. 3. Optical analysis of cobalt-chromium coating. Reflectance spectra of the SS/Co–Cr absorber before and after thermal stability (TS) test, presented with normalized spectra of a black body at 100°C and the AM1.5 direct solar irradiance [38]. The light blue region shows the standard deviation of the measured samples. The coating exhibits a broadband absorbance peak over the solar spectrum before gradually shifting to highly reflecting at longer wavelengths. The spectrum of the SS/Co–Cr TS show a significant degradation in optical properties, indicating a poor thermal stability. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

by Absolicon today, which exhibits $\alpha_s = 0.94$ and $\epsilon_{100} = 0.08$. Based on this, the PVD absorber seems superior. However, for the intended application the solar-to-thermal conversion efficiency of the PVD absorber is $\eta_{s-t} = 0.93$, and consequently inferior to the SS/Co–Cr absorber.

We also note that the SS/Co–Cr absorber is competitive with regards to optical properties compared to both commercial (Energie Solaire with $\alpha_s = 0.95$ and $\epsilon_{100} = 0.15$ on stainless steel) and reported [7,8] black chrome absorbers, as well as other electroplated potential alternatives [18–21,23].

With good optical properties of the pristine SS/Co–Cr surface established, we now turn to the thermal stability of the coating. In Fig. 3 we can see from the reflectance spectra of SS/CoCr TS that exposure to 400°C in air for 24 h have a detrimental effect on the optical properties of the coated surface. The sample exhibits a $\alpha_s = 0.844$ and $\epsilon_{100} = 0.301$ resulting in a $\eta_{s-t} = 0.815$ and, from equation (1), a drop in performance of $PC_{0.07} = 0.131$. An acceptable level of degradation over a standardized ageing test simulating a lifetime in use is $PC \leq 0.05$ [36], so even though the performed test is not standardized, failing to this degree clearly indicates an insufficient thermal stability.

The reflectance spectrum of SS/Co–Cr TS in Fig. 3 gives an indication of the reason for the poor stability. In the infrared region two distinct absorbance peaks are visible at $15,025 \text{ nm}$ and $18,000 \text{ nm}$, which indicate cubic spinel Co_3O_4 [59], and consequently an oxidized coating.

3.4. Addressing thermal stability

It is evident from the deterioration of the optical properties that the coating is not stable at high temperatures in air. To get a better understanding of the degradation process, samples exposed to the thermal stability test (SS/Co–Cr TS) were investigated further.

SEM images of a SS/Co–Cr TS sample show that the morphology of the coating has changed drastically, the sharp ridges and cavities characteristic for the pristine sample (Fig. 1b) are almost completely gone, see Fig. 4a. The outermost ridges are still visible, but except for them, the coating appears to have melted/merged, with collapsed structures and filled cavities. The more compact coating absent of pores or surface structures explains the loss in absorbance for the texture based absorber and should give rise to optical properties closer to the intrinsic

Fig. 4. Thermal stability of cobalt-chromium coating. SEM imaging of the SS/Co-Cr absorber after being exposed to 400 °C for 24 h shows a surface morphology where the structures have collapsed, and the cavities have been filled in (a). The surface of the coating is comprised mainly of Co_3O_4 based on the XPS analysis (b, c). TGA analysis shows that the oxidation of the Co into Co_3O_4 occurs around 440 °C (d). The XRD supports the oxidation to Co_3O_4 but also shows that some hcp Co is left indicating an incomplete oxidation of the coating (e). The Raman spectroscopy results also agree well with Co_3O_4 (f).

properties of the material. The appearance also changes from dark brown-black to a brighter blue which, considering that Co_3O_4 is a blue coloring agent, supports an oxidation to Co_3O_4 indicated by the absorption lines in Fig. 3.

The most pronounced changes revealed by the EDX analysis of SS/Co-Cr TS are increased oxygen and decreased Co concentrations from 17.7 to 46.9% and from 62.7 to 38.4%, respectively, see Fig. S4. The ratio (Co/O) of 0.82 agrees well with an oxidation of nearly all Co in the coating to Co_3O_4 . An interesting feature is the concentration change of Cr and Fe, which have decreased from 2.3 to 1.4% and increased from 1.3 to 4.7%, respectively, indicating diffusion between the substrate and coating. The ratio (Cr/Fe) is 0.29 for SS/Co-Cr TS compared to 0.30 for the substrate (see Table 1), suggesting an almost complete diffusion of Cr from the Co-Cr coating into the substrate.

The samples exposed to the thermal stability test were also analyzed with XPS, Raman, XRD and TGA, see Fig. 4. In Fig. 4b and c the Co 2p and O 1s XPS spectra of a SS/Co-Cr TS sample are presented, see Fig. S6b for entire spectrum. The relative intensities of the main and first satellite peaks of Co at 779.5 and 780.9 eV, respectively, as well as the four satellite peaks indicate a surface composed of Co_3O_4 , as opposed to a mixture with $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$ for the pristine sample [51]. This agrees well with the more intense main peak compared to first satellite for O compared to the pristine sample [52].

In Fig. 4f, the Raman spectrum of a SS/Co-Cr TS sample exhibits clear peaks at 198, 484, 523, 623 and 694 cm^{-1} which is in good agreement both in terms of relative intensities and position with Co_3O_4 [60].

The XRD spectra presented in Fig. 4e of SS/Co-Cr TS and the stainless steel substrate show that most peaks fit well with those of spinel Co_3O_4 [52,61]. In addition to the superimposed peaks from the substrate at 43.55°, 50.65° and 74.55°, the peaks at 42.26° and 47.28° as well as the intensity of the 44.26° peak is attributed to metallic hcp Co, indicating that the coating is not completely oxidized after 24 h at 400 °C [53].

The TGA analysis performed in air shows three exothermic reactions at 335, 440 and 890 °C, see Fig. 4d. The reaction at 335 °C is attributed

to a small amount of cobalt carbonate (CoCO_3) decomposing into Co_3O_4 [62]. The reaction at 440 °C is accompanied by a significant weight gain of 22%, indicating oxidation of a large part of the coating. Based on previous results, this corresponds to an oxidation of metallic Co into Co_3O_4 . This is also supported by a further reaction at 890 °C where the Co_3O_4 is decomposed into CoO [62].

The results are coherent and clearly show that both the metallic Co in the bulk and the $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$ on the surface are oxidized to Co_3O_4 when exposed to the thermal stability test.

3.5. Silica top coating

To prohibit the oxidation of the Co-Cr coating at elevated temperatures, a protective top coating of silica was added. The reflectance spectra used for the spectral analysis of the SS/Co-Cr absorber before and after the addition of the silica coating (SS/Co-Cr/ SiO_2) are presented in Fig. 5, together with normalized spectra of a black body at 100 °C and the AM1.5 direct solar irradiance [38]. The SS/Co-Cr sample exhibits the same characteristics as in Fig. 3 but with optical properties of $\alpha_S = 0.921$ (2), $\epsilon_{100} = 0.149$ (11) and $\eta_{s-t} = 0.906$ (1). The lower absorptance is attributed to batch-to-batch variations. However, the addition of the silica coating significantly improves the optical properties to $\alpha_S = 0.958$ (1), $\epsilon_{100} = 0.124$ (4) and $\eta_{s-t} = 0.946$ (1), an improvement of 4% (units) in solar-to-thermal conversion efficiency. The standard deviation over the entire spectra of both coatings are shown as light blue/green shading.

The low refractive index of silica renders it suitable as an antireflective coating over the solar spectrum, making it a common top layer for solar selective surfaces [63,64]. Furthermore, silica is opaque in the IR region, and consequently it reflects thermal radiation and thereby lowers the emittance. The separation of diffuse and specular reflectance between short and long wavelengths, respectively, is maintained through the addition of the silica layer, but the change is shifted to approximately 1.4 μm , see Fig. S7b.

The thickness of the silica coating is partly undefined due to the

Fig. 5. Optical analysis with silica top coating. The reflectance spectra of the SS/Co-Cr with and without silica (SiO_2), presented with normalized spectra of a black body at 100 °C and the AM1.5 direct solar irradiance [38]. The standard deviation of the spectra is shown as light blue/green regions. The silica top coating has a positive effect on the selectivity of the surface by working as an antireflective coating over most of the solar spectrum and a reflector of thermal radiation in the IR region. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

surface morphology of the underlying Co-Cr coating resulting in minor interference effects. Consequently, the distinct antireflective effect centered around 1 μm derives primarily from the refractive index of the silica being below that of the SS/Co-Cr surface [65,66]. However, in the short wavelength region below the intersection at approximately 450 nm, the relationship has switched, causing a higher reflectance with the silica top coating. Note that an extinction coefficient close to zero [65] gives a negligible absorbance within the silica, meaning that below the first air/silica interface, the absorber generates the absorbance through multiple reflections in the structure, just like in the case without the silica.

The SS/Co-Cr/ SiO_2 absorber was also investigated with SEM and FIB

prior to and after the thermal stability test, see Fig. 6. Though translucent in the SEM image in Fig. 6a, the silica is evident, especially when compared to the SS/Co-Cr absorber in Fig. 1b. The presence of silica is also confirmed by EDX and XPS measurement, see Figs. S5 and S6c. The silica is homogeneously deposited without cracks, and it covers the Co-Cr coating completely, with the only exception at the most protruding underlying structures.

In Fig. 6b and c the cross section of the SS/Co-Cr/ SiO_2 absorber clearly shows the silica coating on top of the Co-Cr layer. The silica has evidently penetrated the cavities of the Co-Cr layer, resulting in a, partly undefined, thickness of approximately 300 nm. Both the cross section and angled view of the silica surface in Fig. 6c and b, respectively, suggests a smooth surface completely covering the Co-Cr, in line with the SEM in Fig. 6a.

The SEM image of the SS/Co-Cr/ SiO_2 absorber after the thermal stability tests in Fig. 6d is at stark contrast to the unprotected coating exposed to the same test, see Fig. 4a. The silica coating clearly has a stabilizing effect at elevated temperatures, manifested by an intact silica layer and an almost entirely intact underlying structure after the tests. We observe however minor effects on the overall structure manifested by that some of the outermost ridges of the Co-Cr coating have penetrated the surface of the silica and undergone some reaction, presumably an oxidation. This is evident in Fig. 6e where a view of the silica surface at an angle clearly shows the protruding ridges. We note that this sample exhibit a slight blue shift in appearance, suggesting that the Co in the ridges protruding through the silica has oxidized to Co_3O_4 , similar to the unprotected coating. From Fig. 6f, where the cross section of the coating is shown, we can see that the high temperature has caused the silica to set into the Co-Cr structure further. This explains the penetration of Co-Cr through the silica surface previously observed. Consequently, the thickness, though irregular, has decreased to approximately 200 nm.

Furthermore, in Fig. 6f we see that the interface between Co-Cr and the stainless steel substrate is more pronounced after the thermal stability test. We speculate that this is related to the diffusion of Cr from the coating to the substrate observed in the EDX analysis.

3.6. Thermal stability with silica top coating

The average optical properties and standard deviation of the three

Fig. 6. Structure with silica top coating. The silica coating is visible as a translucent but homogenous and crack free coating completely covering the underlying Co-Cr coating in the SEM images of the pristine SS/Co-Cr/ SiO_2 coating (a). The cross section show that the silica layer penetrates the cavities of the Co-Cr and is approximately 300 nm thick (b, c). The silica coating is largely unaffected by the thermal stability test and prohibits the Co-Cr coating from collapsing and from oxidation to the most part (d). However, the elevated temperature causes the silica to set further into the Co-Cr structure resulting Co-Cr ridges penetrating the silica surface and a decreased thickness of approximately 200 nm (e, f). Note, the scale bars in b, c, e and f are valid for vertical distances due to sample tilt.

samples being exposed to the thermal stability test with a protective silica coating is presented in Fig. 7a, see details in Table S3. As shown previously (Fig. 5), the addition of the silica top coating improves the selectivity. Here the average solar absorptance and thermal emittance change from 0.91 (1) to 0.95 (1) and 0.20 (2) to 0.18 (1), respectively.

Now, with silica, the average absorptance is perfectly maintained at $\alpha_{S7} = 0.950$ (4) through the thermal stability test, unlike the average emittance which is increased to 0.24 (3). However, the performance criterium, see equation (1), is still well within the allowed degradation of 0.05 [36] at $PC_{0.07} = 0.002$ (10). Note that the degradation is below this limit with the conventional weighting factor of 0.5 as well, with $PC_{0.5} = 0.025$ (20). Additionally, the small standard deviations indicate a coherent group of samples.

Evidently, the silica top coating significantly increases the thermal stability of the Co–Cr coating by largely preventing oxidation and concurrently maintaining the structures of the texture-based absorber. The increased emittance, evident even with the silica, is attributed primarily to diffusion of Cr from the Co–Cr coating to the substrates, a process indicated by EDX of the SS/Co–Cr TS sample and known to have negative effects on the emittance of selective black chrome on stainless steel. In Fig. 6f we can also see that this interface is more pronounced after the thermal stability test.

3.7. Adhesion of the coating

The result of the ASTM D3359 standardized cross hatch adhesion test with and without a silica top coating can be seen in Fig. 7 [37]. From Fig. 7d and e it is evident that both SS/Co–Cr/SiO₂ samples exhibit excellent adhesion with no peeling, resulting in the highest grade of 5B. The SS/Co–Cr samples in Fig. 7b and c also exhibit good adhesion, with grades of 5B and 4B, respectively. However, compared to the silica samples, the cuts are more pronounced, and some peeling is evident in Fig. 7c.

Based on these results, both adhesion and mechanical durability are improved by the silica top coating, and the adhesion is deemed excellent with it. These effects as well as an increased resistance to humidity has been reported for top coatings of silica as well as AlOOH on porous selective coatings [67–69].

4. Conclusion

The selective Co–Cr coating electroplated on a stainless steel

substrate produced a texture-based absorber with a surface morphology of sharp ridges and cavities in the size of 1 μm . The coating is 1.8 μm thick and porous down to the substrate. The bulk of the coating is primarily metallic Co with a hexagonal close-packed crystalline structure. The Cr concentration increases close to the substrate and is essential for a good adhesion of the coating. The coating reacts with air, creating a surface comprised of Co₃O₄ and Co(OH)₂. The absorber exhibits a high selectivity with a solar absorptance and emittance of 0.96 and 0.14, respectively, giving an excellent solar-to-thermal conversion efficiency of 0.95.

When exposed to 400 °C in air for 24 h, the Co in the coating is oxidized into Co₃O₄. The thermal degradation causes the structure of the coating to collapse and Cr to diffuse from the Co–Cr coating to the substrate with a significant degradation of the optical properties as a result. However, applying a protective top coating of silica improves the optical properties, adhesion, mechanical durability, and thermal stability of the absorber. The silica maintains the absorptance through the thermal stability test by preventing both the structural collapse and Co oxidation. With this protective coating we note that we can mitigate the thermal degradation, limiting the loss in performance to $PC_{0.07} = 0.002$, well below the accepted degradation of 0.05. Concurrently we reach competitive optical performance manifested by a solar absorptance and thermal emittance of 0.96 and 0.12, respectively.

The SS/Co–Cr/SiO₂ absorber is cheap, scalable, environmentally sustainable and exhibits competitive optical properties for applications in low-to mid-temperature concentrating solar collectors.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Erik Zäll: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. Andreas Nordenström: Data curation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. Mikael Järn:

Fig. 7. Durability of the silica protected cobalt-chromium absorber. The average optical properties and standard deviation of the samples tested for thermal stability (TS) with a protective silica top coating (a). Adding the silica improves both absorptance and emittance and maintains the absorptance throughout the test. The cross hatch adhesion test of SS/Co–Cr (b, c) and SS/Co–Cr/SiO₂ (d, e) show that all samples have a high adhesion but that the additions of the silica still improves it resulting in a grade of 5B for both SS/Co–Cr/SiO₂ samples [37].

Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jonatan Mossegård:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Thomas Wågberg:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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